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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

FILOLOGIYA TADQIQOTLARI

1. Nazarov Sardor Xasanovich BADIY TARJIMANING LINGVISTIK MUAMMOLARI.....	4
2. Латипов Окил Журакулович КОНЦЕПТ «КОШКА» В АСПЕКТЕ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ИНТЕРПЕТАЦИИ.....	10
3. Шахобиддинова Шохида Ҳошимовна, Рустамов Дилшод Абдувоҳидович СИНЕРГЕТИКА – ТИЛГА ОИД ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРНИНГ ИСТИҚБОЛЛИ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯСИ.....	18
4. Юсупов Ойбек Нематжонович ТАРЖИМА ИЛМИ.....	27

PEDAGOGIKA TADQIQOTLARI

5. Adamandia Z., Kulijanov U. SUCCESS FACTORS OF A SUCCESSFUL DIGITAL STORYTELLING.....	36
6. Bekchonova Shaira Bazarbayevna KIBER TAHDIDLAR INDEKSI.....	44
7. Govindh M. MODERN EDUCATION: IMPORTANCE, CHARACTERISTICS, ADVANTAGES & EFFECTS.....	51
8. Konstantinos G. Karras SOFT SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL WITH A FOCUS ON NEW TECHNOLOGIES THROUGH CRITICAL PEDAGOGY.....	55
9. Leonidas-Dimitrios Kotrogiannos EDUCATION OF VULNERABLE GROUPS THE CASE OF GREECE.....	65
10. M^a Pilar M.C., Celia Navío IDENTIFYING GOOD PRACTICES WHEN IMPLEMENTING STORYTELLING IN THE EFL CLASS.....	73
11. Mamatov Dilmurad Narmuradovich RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TA'LIMDA KORPORATIV HAMKORLIK ASOSLARI.....	79
12. Қўйсинов Одил Алмуротович ЎҚУВЧИЛАРНИНГ МАНТИҚИЙ ФИКРЛАШИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ХАЛҚАРО ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ.....	85

PSIXOLOGIYA TADQIQOTLARI

13. Акрамов Мирмуҳсин Рустамович АХЛОҚИЙ ОНГ ТАБИАТНИ ЭСТЕТИК ИДРОК ҚИЛИШНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК ОМИЛИ СИФАТИДА.....	89
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TARIX TADQIQOTLARI

14. Зоҳидов Қобилжон Тоиржонович СИЙРА ВА ТАБАҚОТ ЖАНРИДАГИ АСАРЛАР АРАБ-МУСУЛМОН ТАРИХИНИ ЎРГАНИШДА МУҲИМ МАНБА.....	95
15. Ишанджанов Бахтиёр Илохомович МОВАРОУННАҲРДА СИЁСИЙ-ИЖТИМОИЙ ВА МАДАНИЙ ҲАЁТ.....	101
16. Саттиев Музаффар Латифович ТОИФ БИТИМИ - СИЁСИЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ САРИ ҚАДАМ.....	106

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MODERN EDUCATION: IMPORTANCE, CHARACTERISTICS, ADVANTAGES & EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

We generally say that the education sector has grown. Modern Education is known as the growth or potential change that entered the education sector. The education that is provided by schools and higher education institutions today is known as Modern Education. Modern education primarily focuses on visualizing, imagining, and thinking. Since practical aspects are more helpful today, educational institutions have started focusing on experimental learning more. It brings up important life skills and facilitates a positive approach towards a sense of responsibility.

Traditional education was undoubtedly effective and inspiring. However, time and surroundings have changed in the last few decades and advancement has intervened. This change has ignited the need for modern education. The purpose of modern education is to prepare future leaders for unforeseen challenges.

Keywords: education, visualizing, imagining, thinking, responsibility, challenges.

Introduction

Modern education is the education given by schools and higher education institutions today. Modern education includes current statistics and the latest study material. Since algorithms, strategies, and methods constantly change, modern education keeps up with the changes. Modern education develops the sense of learning essential life skills, analytic competencies, decision-making skills, and critical thinking. This phase of education is not completely distant from contemporary education. Rather, it is a combination of traditional and modern approaches.

Modern education in India was introduced by Lord Thomas Babington Macaulay. Along with the modern education approach, the English language also came to India. In the 1830s the curriculum was limited to modern subjects. It involved Mathematics, Science, English and philosophy.

Characteristics of Modern Education

Modern education is the current type of education imparted to students. No one claimed it to be entirely different from the traditional patterns. Most of the features or characteristics of modern education and traditional education systems are still identical.

For instance, earlier the students were supposed to attend the classes by being seated in clean rows and hearing the teacher standing up front. Even today, the education pattern is the same.

Some of the characteristics of modern education are-

1. Learner-Centred

One of the most evident characteristics of modern education is that the students are learners and the teachers are still the guides. The curriculums and patterns of teaching are immediately directed towards the portion of learners.

2. Activity-based

The teachers structure the teaching process in the most interesting way. They plan out different types of activities that interest the students. Not only activities but students are also encouraged to participate in class discussions through these patterns. This increases their confidence and improves their way of interacting.

3. Integrative in Nature

Modern education is integrative. The teachers are focused on polishing their students and to do the same, they connect issues from different subjects together. This way the students learn more effectively and efficiently.

4. Resource-based

Being knowledgeable and resourceful are different. Teachers today are resourceful. They gather and spread the information that adds to their student’s knowledge. The teachers following modern education need to be resourceful to make their efforts count.

Modern education is just a term that specifies different characteristics. Despite a lot of differences, the role of modern education and traditional patterns remains the same. The traditional education patterns were directly concentrated on the better learning of the students that is still the same.

Traditional Education Vs Modern Education

Traditional and modern educations are different when it comes to education patterns and approaches. Here are a few differences that will help us understand how traditional education systems are somehow different from modern education systems.

Let's get a better understanding of traditional education vs modern education.

Traditional Education	Modern Education
Traditional Education is teacher-centered. It is one of the most prominent differences between the two types of education systems.	Modern education is learner-centered. The modern approach toward education is more focused on the students and not the teachers.
Yet another characteristic of traditional education that is different from modern education is that it is subject-specific.	The modern approach to education is subjectspecific along with skill-based. The modern approach believes in following the subject patterns but not ignoring the skill set.
The traditional approach to education was one-way. In earlier times, discussions and two-way knowledge spread were not on trend.	Modern education is multi-way. Today, the education system tries to involve the students to participate in discussions. Also, not only in class but the students are encouraged to gain knowledge from different sources.
Traditional education was more focused on theoretical sessions. That time was more about cramming and listening to the teachers.	In contrast to the traditional education system, the modern education system focuses on practical and conceptual teaching. The students are taught through most practical ways to improve their retaining power.

Grading in Modern Education

The grading system has been in continuity for a long time. Students are given their yearly reports which make them understand their growth and decline. The grading system is of course an effective way of motivating students but also demotivates most of them.

The modern education grading system has shown some effective changes. Instead of judging the theoretical knowledge only, the modern approach considers an overall accumulation. Adding theoretical growth with practical improvement gives out grades. The modern education grading system is a refined and more thoughtful version of informing students about where they lack and can improve. The modern grading is a bit subtle if compared to the traditional grading system.

Modern Education Advantages

Modern education has successfully proved to be better than traditional education. Where traditional education was majorly meant for men, modern education is focused on women's empowerment too. The importance of modern education has clearly strengthened its footing amongst schools and parents.

There have been multiple changes in the education system that can be explained through these modern education advantages.

1. Available to Aspiring Students

Unlike traditional education, the modern education system is open and available to people from all walks of life. It is immune to all types of gender, class and age. Modern education has helped the country become a "literate one."

2. Covers Multiple Subject Options

Modern education covers multiple subject options. The modern structure of education has been focused on different subjects that include the potential interests of the students. No matter if the subject is technology focused, it would still be taught.

3. Flexible and Simplified

Modern education system is more flexible and convenient as compared to traditional education. It allows online and supplemental classes through different mediums. Also, it is not strictly based on the book learning but accepts the real knowledgeable answers too.

Modern education is advantageous in many ways. From preparing the students for future challenges to making them more confident, it has been a great change.

Effects of Modern Education

The modern education system has been followed for a long time. Most of the effects of modern education are positive and effective.

Here are some noted effects or advantages of modern education in society.

1. Better Teacher-student Relations

Unlike other education patterns, modern education did not focus on creating fear in students. The teachers were more driven toward improving their student's knowledge and enhancing their future skills. Modern education glued the bond of teachers with the students.

2. Globalization

Since modern approaches were not limited to boundaries. The students started reaching different platforms irrespective of geographical boundaries. Modern culture increased globalization in the education system which ultimately helped the students set a global foothold.

3. New Systems and Education Patterns

Modern education introduced new systems. Since the mediums and platforms diversified during the time, it also allowed the intrusion of better technology and systems. Moreover, the education patterns got renewed for a better result.

The effects of modern education were mostly positive. Since it was inclined towards the betterment of the students, it showed great results.

Which one is Better: Modern Education or Traditional Education?

If we compare modern education and traditional education, there is a minute difference. Of course, the patterns and approaches were different, but the motive was always the same.

Modern education can be claimed to be a better system. Because of the diversification in the subjects and activities, modern systems were more fruitful. It has been concluded that practical knowledge yield better results which were followed by modern education patterns.

So, if we compare, modern education was better than traditional means. It intensifies the inner skills and talent of the students.

Conclusion

Modern education is known to be the best transformation of the education system. It intentionally inclines towards bringing out the best potential of the students. This helps them do better in the future and handle challenges more sensibly. Students in high school and Universities can relate to the changes in the system.

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